

A Conceptual Review of Work Life Balance and Gender and Work Qualitative Literature

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 3

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Farhana Fathima, M., and T. Helan. "A Conceptual Review of Work Life Balance and Gender and Work Qualitative Literature." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S3, 2019, pp. 1–8.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572401>

M.Farhana Fathima

*Doctoral Research Scholar, Department of Management Studies
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti
Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India*

Dr.T.Helan

*Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli
Tamil Nadu, India*

Abstract

Work-life balance is about how we combine work with other areas of our life, such as children, care for the elderly and friends. Poor work-life balance can lead to poor work performance, which further leads to a lack of fulfillment in the job. Work-life balance is basically the positive relationship between work and other equally important activities in life which include family, leisure, personal development and community development issues. The relationship cannot be clearly defined and varies from person to person according to their life demands. Work life balance is intended to allow employees greater flexibility in their working patterns so that they can balance what they do at work with the responsibilities and interests they have outside work. So the researcher attempts to know about the work life conflict, gender and work health in qualitative literature, barriers of work life employees and organizational practices managing issues of work life balance.

Keywords: work life conflict, gender, work, organization.

Introduction

The term "Work Life Balance" was coined in 1956. Work-Life balance is a broad concept which includes proper prioritizing between career and ambition on one hand, compared with pleasure, leisure, family and spiritual development on the other. It is a key factor which determines employee satisfaction, loyalty and productivity. The current work force scenario is marked by the fast pace of change, intense pressure, constant deadlines, changing demographics, increased use of technology and the work from home concept. Also with the increase in the proportion of dual earner families and the kind of life style finance people are having work life conflicts are inevitable. Work life Balance has important consequences for employee – attitude towards their organizations. A balance between work and life is supposed to exist when is proper functioning at work and also at home.

Work life balance is an area of increasing importance to both employees and employers. Employees need it to balance work and non-work roles and employers require it to increase productively and reduce cost (Abbott & De Cieri, 2008). The drivers for work life balance can be attributed to changes in the demographic distribution of the labour force, technological advancement and the 24/7 opening hour's culture in Morden society (Beauregard & Henry, 2009; Kalliath & Brough, 2008). While there is no consistent definition of work-life balance, there are some consistent themes which have emerged these include: employees achieving an acceptable balance between their work and personal lives, employers work initiative which would aid improve employees productivity providing a range of targeted work-life initiatives that enhance firm performance and not result into considerable increase in cost to the employers (De Cieri, Holmes, Abbott & Pettit, 2005).

Work-life balance involves proper prioritizing between “work” (career and ambition) on the one hand and “life” (Health, pleasure, leisure, family and spiritual development) on the other. Related, though broader, terms include “lifestyle balance” and “life balance”. Work-life balance, in its broadest sense, is defined as a satisfactory level of involvement or ‘fit’ between the multiple roles in a person’s life. Kossek & Ozeki (1998). Observing the day to day lives of many employees, two main issues to be addressed to achieve work life balance are time and stress. Managing these two variables is the secret of a perfect work life balance. Thus formula of work life balance: Work life balance = Time management + Stress management. As derived by Gupta and Sharma (2013).

From the very beginning it is important to understand that work-life balance does not mean to devote an equal amounts of time to paid work and non-paid roles; in its broadest sense, is defined as a satisfactory level of involvement or ‘fit’ between the multiple roles in a person’s life. Although definitions and explanations may vary, work-life balance is generally associated with equilibrium between the amount of time and effort somebody devotes to work and personal activities, in order to maintain an overall sense of harmony in life. (Clarke, et al 2004, 121). To understand work-life balance, it is important to be aware of the different demands upon us and our personal resources- our time and our energy- that we can deploy to address them. With this awareness, we are able to review and value the choices we have in terms of how we allocate our precious resources. Such conscious decision-making provides a sense of control over our working arrangements in order to better accommodate other aspects of our lives, while still benefiting the organizations. Kumar and Mohd (2014) says that Work life balance is about people having measure of control over when, where and how they work. There is a view that work-life balance only in the framework of what the company does for the individuals.

Objectives of the Study

1. To know about the basic concepts of Work Life conflict among employees.
2. To found Gender, health and Work Life Balance qualitative literature.
3. To study about the challenges and faced by the employees.
4. To know organizational addressing issues of employees in work life balance

Work-Family Conflict

The phrase ‘work-family conflict’ (or work-home conflict) emerged in the 1980s (Barnett, 1999; Barnett & Gareis, 2006), having its origins in the study of multiple roles (Eby, Casper, Lockwood, Bordeaux, & Brinley, 2005). As with role strain, work-family conflict focuses on tensions arising from women combining reproductive and productive roles (Hammer & Thompson, 2003). Corporate-cultures at the time “explicitly required family matters to be left at the work-place door” (Barnett & Gareis, 2006: p.210). This conceptualization of work and family as separate entities, competing for time, energy and attention (Barnett, 1998; Marks, 1977), led to the characterization

of “constant tension and perpetual conflict” (Barnett & Gareis, 2006: p.210), as represented by work-family conflict.

One common criticism of work-family conflict is that studies have examined work-family conflict in general, ignoring the direction of conflict (Eagle, Miles, & Icenogle, 1997; Emslie et al., 2004), namely work-to-family (work conflicting with family life) or family to- work (family life conflict with work). Studies that have taken into account the direction of conflict have found mixed results. Work-to-family conflict has been found to be more prevalent than family-to-work conflict (Eagle et al., 1997; Frone, Russell, & Cooper, 1992; Swanson, Power, & Simpson, 1998). Some studies have found women experience higher levels of work-to-family conflict than men, but there is no gender difference in family-to work conflict (McElwain, Korabik, & Rosin, 2005). Others have found different associations with health measures, for example finding work-to-family conflict, but not family-to-work conflict, to be associated with poor health (Adams, King, & King, 1996; Grandey & Cropanzano, 1999; Hammer, Saksvik, Nytro, Torvatn, & Bayazit, 2004) (although one study found the reverse (Noor, 2004), with family-to-work conflict being associated with lack of well-being). Furthermore, gender differences have been found in these associations with health, with family-to-work conflict being associated with poor health for men but not women, whereas work-to-family conflict was associated with poor health for women but not men (Macewen & Barling, 1994).

The work-family conflict model has been critiqued on other grounds. Firstly, it presupposes conflict, whereas a more accurate representation of life may be “one in which work and family are seen as overlapping spheres that are often in harmony” (Barnett, 1998: p.217). Furthermore, the model prioritises the spheres of ‘work’ and ‘family’ above all others, potentially ignoring individuals without children, and drawing a divide between the two spheres which may not allow for different conceptions of work (for example, unpaid domestic work (Oakley, 1974)).

The concept of ‘work-family balance’, “the extent to which individuals are equally involved in - and equally satisfied with – their work role and their family role” (Greenhaus & Singh, 2003), goes some way to addressing these concerns, suggesting that giving equal priority to both roles can reduce or even resolve conflict (Gregory & Milner, 2007)

Methodology

This study is a conceptual one and descriptive in nature with a detailed review of literature. The secondary data and information have been analyzed for preparing the paper extensively. The secondary information have been collected from different scholars and researchers published books, articles published in different journals, periodicals, conference paper, working paper and websites good journals and research papers were also required during the study.

Gender and Work

Work has always taken a principal position in the lives of human beings. Gender is one of the universal dimensions on which status differences are based. It is a social construct specifying the socially and culturally prescribed roles that males and females are to follow. It involves those social, cultural and physiological aspects linked to males and females through particular social contexts. The roles of females and males are usually defined differently in different cultures. In the last couple of decades there has been increased interest in exploring factors influencing workers satisfaction with specific focus on gender differences. Irrespective of society, women have been perceived as care-givers, mothers and wives whose principal occupations are child rearing and taking care of the domestic concerns. In contrast, males are burdened with reverberating duties of political, economic and military performances that entail courage.

Women's domestic tasks and child care influence the kind of work they favor, since flexibility (in terms of hours and relative ease of entry, exit and re-entry) allow them to merge work and family duties more effortlessly. Women seem to be drawn to jobs where either due to their inclinations and attributes employers prefer to employ women. While economic theories indicate that occupations may develop into 'female' occupations due to sex stereotyping, new-classical economic and human capital theory posits that the partiality of women and employers result in the absorption of women in flexible jobs. Therefore while domestic duties increase women's preferences for flexibility in jobs, the stereotyping of some jobs can also influence the kind of jobs available to them. Recent global trends indicate a pointed reduction in the masculine role of provider. There is now a significant increase in female labor participation arising to some extent from the deterioration in the supreme power of men brought about by swelling degrees of unemployment and underemployment.

Gender, work-life balance and health: qualitative literature

This section presents an overview of literature which has investigated the relationship between work-life balance and health, again divided into quantitative and qualitative sections.

Only two studies with a qualitative element examined gender differences in the relationship between work-life balance and health, both finding that gender norms had an impact on work-life balance on health. A study of employed parents in Australia (Bryson et al., 2007) found that demand overload was intensified by gender norms and social expectations such as being a 'good' mother and the dominance of male employment (a 'good' provider) in providing for the family. This, combined with consumption pressures, led to increased levels of stress and tiredness amongst participants. A study of immigrant Latino poultry workers in the United States (Grzywacz et al., 2007) found, whilst overall levels of work-family conflict were very low, women reported higher levels of conflict than men, with the physical demands of work contributing to women's work-family conflict. The study found that these gender differences were partly due to the women having responsibility for the domestic sphere, and therefore the physical and emotional exhaustion caused by work had a greater impact on their family life.

Gender and work-life balance: qualitative literature

Quantitative studies do not shed light on how women and men "understand and negotiate the intersections between work and home life" (Emslie & Hunt, 2009: p.154). However, relatively few qualitative studies compared women's and men's perceptions of work-life balance. Most of the studies found that conflict reported by participants was exacerbated by gendered norms and expectations (Bacik & Drew, 2006; Backett, 1982; Bryson et al., 2007; Charles & Harris, 2007; Connell, 2005; Emslie & Hunt, 2009; Grzywacz, Arcury, Marin, Carrillo, Burke, Coates et al., 2007; Halford, 2006; Halford, Svage, & Witz, 1997; Hatten et al., 2002; Hilbrecht, Shaw, Johnson, & Andrey, 2008; James, in press; Laegran, 2008; Linehan & Walsh, 2000; Loscocco, 1997; Speakman & Marchington, 1999; Sullivan & Lewis, 2001). The importance of socio-economic factors was considered in a small number of studies (Backett-Milburn, Airey, McKie, & Hogg, 2008; Weigt & Solomon, 2008), as was the impact of parenthood on experiences of work-life balance (Bruening & Dixon, 2008; James, in press; Linehan & Walsh, 2000; Stockley & Daly, 1999).

A study of UK home-based teleworkers (Sullivan & Lewis, 2001) found that, whilst the majority of women and men reported that working from home led to a breakdown of boundaries between work and home, women and men experienced this in different ways. Working from home allowed women to perform multiple roles, continuing to fulfill their domestic responsibilities whilst accomplishing their financial and personal need to work, thereby reinforcing gendered

expectations of work and family. For men, the flexibility gained from working from home allowed them to work long hours, thereby reinforcing gendered norms around work. The men in the study reported higher levels of interference between work and home than the reverse, reinforcing the normalized legitimacy of work interfering with family for men, and family interfering with work for women. This reinforcement of gendered norms was supported by a study of fathers in the United Kingdom who worked from home several days a week for an insurance firm (Halford, 2006). Whilst participants found some changes to their fathering patterns and involvement, this was viewed as “unearned and unexpected, a perk that they would regret losing, but did not expect to keep” (p.399), with the fathers’ roles being inextricably entwined with that of provider.

Loscocco (1997) found similarly gendered experiences in her study of self-employed people in the United States. Women and men were found to fulfil gender norms in different ways, with women accommodating work to fit with family life, whereas men prioritised their business. As with Sullivan and Lewis’ (2001) study of home-based teleworkers, understandings of flexibility were gendered. Women emphasized the importance of flexibility in balancing their paid employment and family responsibilities, whereas men saw flexibility as a symbol of control, rarely making use of flexibility for work-life balance needs.

A study of fathers working across a range of organisations in the United Kingdom (Hatten al., 2002) found that work-place culture played a large role in participants’ experiences of work life balance. For example, many employers expected work to be the primary focus of male workers’ lives, thereby leaving little space for family commitments. This was reinforced by the assumption amongst participants that flexibility of working patterns in order to accommodate caring responsibilities was acceptable for working mothers but not for fathers. Gendered assumptions about care and flexibility were perpetuated both at an organizational-level, and by the workers themselves.

It should be noted that some studies found reported differences within as well as between women and men. For example, the study of home-based teleworkers (Sullivan & Lewis, 2001) found that parental status and career involvement mediated women’s experiences of work-life balance, with women with young children reporting higher levels of family to work interference, and women with high career involvement experiencing higher levels of intrusion from work to family.

The family is a primary site where gender norms are reproduced (Loscocco, 1997), and thereby parenthood has been found to exacerbate gender norms and differences in experiences of work-life balance (Bruening & Dixon, 2008; Linehan & Walsh, 2000; Stockley & Daly, 1999). For example, a study of mothers working as head coaches for sporting institutions in the United States (Bruening & Dixon, 2008) found that “the dramatic life changes associated with the birth of the first child illuminated the gendered nature of the sports industry” (p.21). Furthermore, the importance of support from family and employers was reported to be essential to ensure participants ‘survived and thrived’ (p.20) as coaches and mothers, a factor which had not been a consideration prior to parenthood.

Few studies considered the impact of class on experiences of work-life balance. However, a comparative analysis of working mothers in low-income, service sector jobs, and assistant professors in the United States (Weigt & Solomon, 2008) found interesting intersectional ties between class and gender. As might be expected, the assistant professors were more able to manage work and family demands due to greater access to resources, whereas the low-income women’s experiences of work-family management was inextricably tied to “making ends meet” (p.641). However, class had an additional impact on gender for the two groups, being found to ‘mute’ gendered experiences for the assistant professors, whilst it intensified them for the low-income, service sector group. For example, the low-income workers reported “gendered interpersonal work

of managing supervisors' or employers' impressions and emotions" (p.642) in order to obtain flexibility, whereas the assistant professors were found to have better access to institutional policies and therefore avoided this interpersonal work. Furthermore, the higher incomes of the assistant professors meant they were better able to pay for childcare than the low-income women.

Williams (2000) observes that in spite of the more flexible schedules, working mothers prefer full-time work. Since part-time work usually receives less interesting and challenging assignments; taking these assignments and working part-time may hinder advancement and growth. Again arising from the fear of marginalization (a product of incongruity with the model employee structure) many might not employ part-time options even when such is available. King (2008) adds that some mothers are challenged by the maternal wall (signified by the less striking assignments billed to them) on their return to work implying also that because they are mothers, they are unable to operate as model workers. Where an organization puts in place work life balance options to improve their work-life obligations, then broad organizational customs must be realigned in a way that the picture of the model worker embraces workers that of a necessity run homes, children, elderly parents, etc.

Williams and Boushey (2010) observes that at the pinnacle of the organizational ladder, most of the persons are males, and suppositions can be made about their deficient individual familiarity with the direct and indirect results of work-family conflict. Some may be single and therefore have no idea of the extent of 'normal' family needs. Others who are married may have spouses who do not go out to work (but are at home as exclusive care providers to the house and children) as a result of the requirements of the positions occupied by the husbands. The incongruous here is that these are the persons that make and restructure organization policies and strategies which invariably generate organizational norms that employees have to abide with.

The Barriers or Challenges to the Work-Life Balance

1. Not for Implementation work only paper: Many organizations have policies that on paper. There is very less of concern for the implementation of the policies.
2. Lack of communication: communication about the programs work/life is essential. Although an organization may offer a rich menu of benefits work/life, the desired effect of the positive effects the results of the company is unlikely to occur if the employees do not know on the programs or understand.
3. The team work: the introduction, the exploitation and the implementation of the work-life balance requires the collaborative work and is in large part a holistic process.
4. Time: The implementation of a strategy of the WLB takes time. The deadlines for implementation must be realistic
5. The size and structure of the Organization: The size and structure of an organization can present difficulties in the implementation of the human resources policy. The introduction of elements of work-life balance policy through a pilot program for example, working at home may have been more interesting than to engage the whole organization.
6. Support of the Employer: Initiatives in place of work of any kind are likely to fail if they do not have the full support of all levels of management. The support and training of managers in the application of the WLB is imperative. Beginning of the commitments with the executives results in a higher level of commitment.
7. The early awareness: early awareness sessions for managers on the work-life concept could have helped to mitigate the initial concerns.
8. The delays in the decision-making: more dependence on working groups to delay the decision.

9. Difference of interpretation: flexible working practices can lead to different interpretations leading to the inconsistency of the approach. The management of performance must be treated in the appropriate manner.
10. Champions of the WLB: Increase of the physical presence of the project officer. champion can allow a better monitoring of the pilot projects. At the beginning of the use of the tool of communication dedicated intranet would have been able to provide a greater concentration to the communication on the work and results of the project the need for clarity for the terms of reference of the working groups and the roles and responsibilities of the members of the group.

When compared to the practices of the WLB grouped isolated: there is something of a puzzle on the reasons for which family-friendly policies and practices. do not appear to improve the balance of work and personal life to the extent where we can expect. The practices favorable to the family will have little impact, but that a comprehensive set of practices are associated with assessments of superior quality of the performance of business. Although their focus is on the performance of the company, there may be consequences similar to their impact on the employees. An interpretation of the presence of a set of practices is that they have become an integral part of the culture of the organization while the insulation and exploitation on the margin. This would reinforce the importance to take into account the organizational culture and climate as a unit of analysis as far as the specific practices. (Mehtha, 2012).

Organizational practices addressing work life issues of employees

The range of Work Life Balance initiatives by the organizations available can be grouped into 3 main areas:

1. Leave provisions (such as parental and family leave): Facilities like Careers Leaves, Opportunity for leave if Care arrangements for children or other dependents breakdown, Study / training leave, Career Breaks, Cultural / religious leave, Bereavement leave, Pooling of leave entitlements are offered by many organizations to the female employees to manage the work life issues . Maternity and Parenting policies like Unpaid maternity /paternity and adoption leave, Paid maternity leave, Paid paternity leave, Paid adoption ,Opportunity to return to the same job after maternity / paternity and adoption leave, Safety at work during pregnancy (e.g. changing the work of pregnant women to avoid long periods of standing or lifting heavy objects), Pre-natal leave (e.g. time for pregnant women or their partners to attend medical appointments during working hours , either using additional leave or sick leave), Staggered return to work after pregnancy (employees being able to negotiate a temporary reduction in hours of work when they return to work) etc are adopted by many organizations to address the issues of work life balance.
2. Flexible hours provisions: Flexible work arrangements like job sharing, flexible start and finish times, Telecommuting, Cap on overtime, Opportunity to negotiate part-timework for full time employees, Time Off in lieu and roistered days off are offered by many organizations.
3. Additional work provisions: Telephone for personal use, counseling services for employees, Referral services for employee's personal needs, Health programs, Parenting or family support programs, Exercise facilities, Relocation or placement assistance, Equal access to promotion, training and development are some of the other provisions by the organizations to support the work life issues of female employees.

Impact of Work Life Imbalance

It can be tempting to rack up hours at work, especially if you're trying to earn a promotion or manage an ever-increasing workload. Sometimes overtime may even be required. If you're spending most of your time working, though, your home life will take a hit. Consider the consequences of poor work-life balance:

1. **Fatigue or Low Energy Levels:** When you're tired, your ability to work productively and think clearly may suffer — which could take a toll on your professional reputation or lead to dangerous or costly mistakes. At the same time when employees feel fatigue due to tiresome work at professional front, when they return home they are left with no energy to interact with family members.
2. **More pressure on household work:** Due to excessive pressure at home front female employees complaint getting late very frequently to job.
3. **Lost time with friends and loved ones.** If you're working too much, you may miss important family events or milestones. This can leave you feeling left out and may harm relationships with your loved ones. It's also difficult to nurture friendships if you're always working.
4. **Increased expectations:** If you regularly work extra hours, you may be given more responsibility. This may lead to only more concerns and challenges. The various roles we occupy as parents, partners and employees or employers bring with them different obligations which need to be reconciled. Balancing work, family and lifestyle commitments is often difficult and sometimes the different demands can be overwhelming and incompatible. The consequences include increases in juvenile crime, more drug abuse, are deduction in care of the community and in community participation and less willingness to take responsibility for care of elderly relatives and for the disadvantaged. While steps to redress these concerns transcend work and employment, it is nevertheless argued that the demands of work contribute to a reduced participation in non-work activities resulting in an imbalance.

Conclusion

Work life balance initiatives designed to help employees balance their work and personal lives are not only an option, but necessity for a employers today. The result of work life imbalance at the workplace can be that employees are less productive. They remain absent more often, or for longer, they never disclose the real reasons for their absence, may have lower levels of morale, more stressed and more stressed and more likely to leave a workplace unsupportive of work-life balance issues.

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